

STRUCTURAL-SEMANTIC AND LINGUOCULTURAL ANALYSIS OF PHRASEOLOGY WITH A PHYTONYMIC COMPONENT IN THE ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

The problem of studying phytonymic phraseology is especially relevant, because phytonyms play a significant role in human life, not only in decorative and aesthetic refraction, but also participate in the transmission of religious, symbolic, aesthetic and mythological ideas. The use of phytonymic phraseological units in speech is very important, since their study introduces students to the cultural component in terms of language learning.

Key words: *phraseological units, phytonyms, phytonymic phraseological units, structural analysis, semantic analysis, linguocultural analysis.*

INTRODUCTION. In connection with the above, phraseology is a special branch of linguistics that studies stable phrases with complex semantics, called phraseological units or phraseological units. The main directions of this science are: idiomatics, phraseomatics, as well as idiomatics. semantic, structural and functional features of a phraseological unit are a set of features that comprehensively limit it from other linguistic units.

A phraseological unit is a stable combination of words that expresses a holistic meaning, and the function is correlated in one word. In the system of phraseological units in the English language, the same phenomena are characteristic of the lexical

composition of the Uzbek language: ambiguity; homonymy; synonymy; antonyms. Thus, the role of phraseological units in the English-language and Uzbek-language pictures of the world most clearly and accurately reflects the spirit of the people, their national mentality, as well as the cultural and historical experience of the world of knowledge, thanks to its expressiveness and emotionality, which contributes to the comprehensive development of the student's personality, sensitivity to the Uzbek and foreign culture [1, p7].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY. Analysis methods such as typological, etymological, component analysis, cross-cultural analysis are used in the article.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS. Concept study is important in modern linguistics. However, any attempt to understand the essence of the concept is related to the number of different points of view. Intensive studies in the field of cognitive linguistics have shown an imbalance in the understanding of the concept of "concept". And the differences found cause uncertainty and terminological confusion.

The term "concept" is an "umbrella" term because it "covers" the subject areas of several scientific directions. First of all, this phenomenon is observed more in such scientific directions as cognitology and cognitive linguistics, which deal with the problems of information processing, thinking and consciousness, as well as linguistic and cultural studies. At the current stage of linguistics, there are several approaches to understanding the concept. Researchers from different countries look at the concept as a linguistic-cognitive, psycholinguistic, linguistic-cultural, cultural or linguistic phenomenon. Each approach, on the basis of some characteristics, emphasizes its own limit of the concept. There are two approaches based on showing the connections between language and culture and the role of concepts in language formation.

We consider the idea of concept structure to be methodologically important. According to U.S. Stepanov: the concept of "1) the main, real sign; 2) additional or insignificant, but historically significant passive characters; 3) the internal form usually has no meaning at all, the meaning is understood in the external form". The first

component - the main, real sign of the concept - is important, known to all speakers of a certain language or culture. Verbally expressed is a means of communication for representatives of a certain ethnic community, nation, people, on the contrary, the second component is an additional, passive sign of the concept - it reveals its relevance far from the entire ethnic group; it exists for representatives of a certain social group, for a certain social stratum. The third component - the etymological sign or internal form - is the least important for the language and concept carriers of any culture, since the history of the word is mainly a science practiced by experts in this field.

To date, phraseologism is being studied as a separate language unit. We will not be mistaken if we say that the objects of study of phraseology, their grammatical features were studied in one way or another, and their stylistic possibilities prompted the creation of large-scale monographic works and phraseological explanatory dictionaries. For the first time in Uzbek linguistics, the linguist scientist A. Reshchad by Mamatov, phraseologism is defined as follows: "Phraseologism is a stable lexical-semantic unit, which is structurally equivalent to a phrase or a sentence, has a generalized meaning, and whose lexical elements have a partial or complete transitive meaning." In our opinion, this description is quite close to the truth. In addition, the linguist distinguishes 4 classifications within the framework of the formation of phraseology of the Uzbek language.

1. In relation to the activity and psyche of the person;
2. Occupation dependence;
3. Based on animal images;
4. Phraseologisms formed in terms of dependence on religion and religious people.

Many different approaches have been used, but nevertheless, the vocabulary of word combinations and their place at the boundaries of this level is still one of the topical issues of linguistics. The synchronic (semantic) classification of phraseological units classified by V.V. Vinogradov is the most popular, which gave a strong impetus

to the purely lexicological treatment of the material. Thus, phraseological units are defined as lexical complexes with specific semantic properties and classified accordingly. The classification of the linguist is based on the motivation of the unity of the phraseological unit and the connection between the meanings of its components. This classification is based on semantic criteria and was proposed by Academician Vinogradov within the framework of phraseological units. He talks about three types of phraseological units, including compounds with a very low level of motivation, we cannot guess the whole meaning from the meaning of its components, they are very idiomatic and cannot be literally translated into other languages.

The study of phraseological units contributes to the formation of linguistic competence, in particular the idea of phraseology as an integral, integral part of the development of the Uzbek and foreign languages. Many plants have been symbols of England since the reign of Queen Victoria of England. These symbols allow you to study the peculiarities of the culture of the people, their values, traditions, realities [2, p45]. A symbol is a sign of reality that, in addition to its object-figurative meaning, carries another, culturally more valuable content. Plants can embody mythological ideas about the world around them, concretize them, which allows them to be considered archetypal symbols.[4, p78]

There are two groups of the estimated potential of phytonyms.

1. The evaluation component can be controlled by the objective properties of the plant: appearance features, usefulness for practical activities, edibility or inedibility, etc.

2. The evaluation component can be determined by the cultural characteristics of plants - the religious mythological origin of plant names, similarity with household items or parts of the body (human, animal, etc.) Semantic features appear in the language; the picture of the world is the most important system-forming function: precisely in accordance with the semantic features common to a number of meanings, lexical units form series, groups and paradigms, that is, the lexical system of a

language. In the English-language picture of the world, there are phytonyms with the element of the devil or the devil, interpretations of negative concepts that are often found in the names of plants with negative properties. In phytonyms, the word formation lady + artifact is often found: handbag - "shepherd's purse", nightcap - "bindweed", ladybug; women's glove - "meadow core", etc. This speaks of the peculiarities of the structure of the women's world in the era of Queen Victoria. Here the similarity is that the plant spreads its stems above the ground, as if the hand of a blind man is groping for something to obtain information; lion's mouth, lit. "lion's mouth" - "snapdragon". [5, p2]The similarity here is that open flowers resemble the open mouth of a lion, hence in the Uzbek language it is also associated with the mouth of a lion. In general, in English phytonomic vocabulary, complete equivalence or complete coincidence of meaning and components occurs frequently. Here the so-called cultural factors. When comparing the cultural components of the English-speaking picture of the world, two groups of factors were identified: 1) universal and 2) national-specific.[3, p101]

Therefore, the study of phytonyms in the linguoculturological aspect is a linguistic picture of the world, which is reflected in the semantics of linguistic units through a system of meanings and associations of the word with a special culturally specific meaning.

Summary. Phraseologisms form the cultural self-awareness of the people and the linguistic picture of the world. Studying phraseological units helps to understand the specifics of people and learn the language. Using the example of the phraseological units under consideration, one can clearly understand the diversity and expressiveness of phraseological units of the modern Uzbek language and English, how similar they are and how they differ from each other.

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